

10 Years of Research Data Management at the University of St Andrews: progress, challenges and future goals

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About us

St Andrews

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University of St Andrews

[University](#) > [Research](#) > [Environment](#) > Schools, centres and institutes

Students

- 10,324 students
- 8,388 undergraduates
- 1,846 postgraduates

Staff

- 3,250 staff
- 4 faculties
- 19 schools
- 30 units

Schools, centres and institutes

The majority of research at the University of St Andrews takes place within academic Schools. However, the University also supports a large number of world-class, often cross-disciplinary or cross-institutional, research centres or institutes.

Research centres and institutes are both concerned with research collaboration, but institutes also provide undergraduate and postgraduate teaching.

Find out more about the research and associated centres and institutes within each University School and Department.

[Art History](#)

[Biology](#)

[Chemistry](#)

[Classics](#)

[Computer Science](#)

[Divinity](#)

[Earth and Environmental Sciences](#)

[Economics and Finance](#)

[English](#)

[Film Studies](#)

[Geography and Sustainable
Development](#)

[Graduate School for Interdisciplinary
Studies](#)

[History](#)

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[Philosophy](#)

[Physics and Astronomy](#)

[Psychology and Neuroscience](#)

[Social Anthropology](#)

Research data management at St Andrews

- The Research Data Management service was introduced in May 2015
- Started with 1 FTE (1 team member), currently ~2 FTEs (3 team members)
- Advice on funders' policies, data management plans, data sharing and best practice in data management
- Training to staff and postgraduate students
- Monitoring for open data and data access statement
- Research data management policy introduced in 2015 and updated in 2023: <https://www.st-andrews.ac.uk/policy/research-open-research/research-data-management-policy.pdf>
- Pure is the institutional data repository

Achievements

Open data rates

- Implemented a monitoring process: targeted advocacy and promotion and increased open data rates

Deposit of data underpinning theses

- 18-month project (2017-2018)
- Collaboration between: Research Data Management team, E-Theses team and Registry
- A **strong encouragement**, not a requirement (yet), to deposit data underpinning theses

DMPs for postgraduate students

- Since academic year 2021-2022
- First-year postgraduate research students are required to submit a data management plan (DMP) as part of their first-year progress review
- Support offered by RDM team includes:
 - Template
 - Training sessions
 - Writing workshops
 - On-to-one consultations
 - DMPs reviews

Service manuals

- A series of documents describing internal processes for the RDM team
- Step by step instructions for different workflows
- Increase resilience within the team
- Consistency across team members
- Living document
- All team members can contribute to it but there is only one owner

Collaborations

- We strengthened relationships with other units:
 - Registry – data underpinning theses
 - IT Services - storage
 - Research & Innovation – compliance and repository
 - Ethics – sensitive data sharing
- Essential to raise RDM awareness in the institution
- Increases chances of success in projects

Challenges

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Introducing change

- Bottom-up approach
- Need approval from various committees
- Dependencies from other departments/units
- Users' acceptance
- Reaching everyone affected

General

- Data in the humanities
- Moving towards FAIR
- Holding boundaries
- Research data storage
- Systems

Lessons learnt

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- We need to communicate change to users well ahead of time
 - Emails
 - Information sessions
 - Include motivation for change
- Not all change will be welcome
- Establish and communicate service boundaries well and clearly
- Strong relationships with colleagues in other units are important
- Document internal processes to increase team resilience

Future goals

What's next?

Short-medium term

- Possibly procure a new data repository
- Work with IT Services to review our institutional storage provision
- Work with Arts & Humanities schools on the DMPs for postgraduate students
- Review our training provision

Next 10 years

- Mandate data deposit for theses
- Mandate DMPs for all projects
- Implement an archive for sensitive data
- Further increase open data rates irrespective of funding

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